

Nurses' Knowledge, Attitudes and Practices Towards Prevention of Pressure Ulcers at Kilimanjaro Christian Medical Center

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Abstract:- Pressure ulcer (PU) is a preventable medical complication of immobility. It has psychological, economic and social impact on individual and family. Globally, studies show that nearly 700,000 patients are affected by pressure ulcers each year. Around 186,617 patients develop a new pressure ulcer in acute care each year. Pressure ulcers are accountable for 2% of preventable deaths. Although PU prevention remains a concern for all healthcare practitioners, maintenance of skin integrity and PU prevention is primarily role of nurses. The study objective as to assess the knowledge, attitudes and practices towards prevention of PU among nurses working at KCMC. The study was a hospital based descriptive cross section study, conducted in August 2020. The study population involved employed nurses at KCMC hospital available during the study period and who meet the inclusion criteria. The sample size consisted of all 141 nurses caring for patients with or at risk of PU and who were willing to participate in the study. Data were analyzed using SPSS (version 20). Frequencies, means, and standard deviations were used to summarize socio-demographic characteristics and to determine mean scores of knowledge, attitudes and practices among participants. A p-value of 0.05 was considered as significant. The study finds that the majority of nurses 106 (75.2%) had low level of knowledge ($\leq 69\%$). Also nurses 87 (61.7%) in this study exhibited positive attitude towards PU prevention. Nearly half (45.4%) of nurses had moderate level of practice towards PU prevention. Knowledge of the nurses regarding prevention of PU was low. The majority of nurses had a positive attitude toward PU prevention. Majority of nurses had moderate practice towards prevention of PU. A non-negligible proportion of nurses had low level of practice towards prevention of PU. Its recommended that continuing professional development can be used to raise nurses' knowledge scores and their use of PU preventative practices.

Keywords:- Knowledge, Attitude, Practice, Pressure Ulcers, KCMC.

I. INTRODUCTION

The pressure ulcers are described to localized injury to the skin and/or underlying tissue usually over a bony prominence as a result of pressure, or pressure in combination with shear and/or friction," by the National Pressure Ulcer Advisory Panel (NPUAP) and European Pressure Ulcer Advisory Panel (EPUAP). Preventing anything from happening or emerging is referred to as prevention. Management is defined as the prevention, treatment, and care of diseases, disorders, and individuals who experience them. A medical complication of immobility that can be avoided is nonetheless a pressure ulcer. It affects a person's and their family's psychologically, economically, and socially. All healthcare professionals have a duty in prevention of pressure ulcers, but nurses have a particularly important responsibility.

According to Munoz, N. (2021), each year, 700,000 patients worldwide suffer from pressure ulcers. Each year, about 186,617 individuals receiving acute treatment acquire a new pressure ulcer. 2% of avoidable fatalities are caused by pressure ulcers. For pressure ulcers to be effectively prevented, three essential elements must be present: awareness of the problem's importance, a proactive attitude toward prevention, and sufficient information. Pressure ulcer prevalence in Sub-Saharan Africa ranges from 3.4% to 18.6%. Between 27 to 46% of patients in low- and middle-income nations have pressure ulcers; however, it's thought that this number may be understated. Furthermore, 4.32% of people in east Africa have pressure ulcers. Locally, there appears to have been little, if any, research on this illness.

PU pose the significant problem for patients, caregivers, and family members. In addition to pain and suffering, patients may also become functionally impaired, which would result in higher costs and longer hospital stays. Treatment for PU in the United States cost roughly 10.2 billion USD in 2008, and it was linked to about 29,000 hospital fatalities. According to estimates, the cost of PU therapy is twice as high as that of prevention. One's daily routine and quality of life are directly impacted by PU. Living with pressure ulcers can have a number of detrimental effects, such as discomfort, fear, worry, social isolation, and decreased independence (Njau,2019).

According to Nuru, (2015) it has been demonstrated that a nurse's expertise and disposition in a certain area have a significant impact on the caliber of care they offer. In order to reduce PU and their associated costs generally, nurses' understanding of pressure ulcers, risk factors, phases, complications, and the use of various scales to predict pressure ulcer risk of development is vital

According to Baker, (2013) a study conducted in Tanzania on individuals with spinal cord injuries revealed PU as a prominent consequence, with an incidence of 22.9%. There is little study information pertaining to nurses' knowledge, attitudes, and practices surrounding pressure ulcers in Tanzania. As a result, we undertook a study to evaluate nurses' knowledge, attitudes, and practices about pressure ulcers in order to provide the nurses, hospital administration, and other researchers with information on potential interventions. The existing nurses' knowledge, attitudes and practices towards prevention of pressure ulcers as the key topic that this study seeks to address. The following specific objectives were addressed as part of the study's overall objective 1) To assess the level of knowledge towards pressure ulcers prevention among nurses 2) To assess the attitudes towards pressure ulcers prevention among nurses. 3) To assess practice towards prevention of pressure ulcers among nurses.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Based on the ideas of systems theory, Martha E. Rogers created her model of unitary humans. According to Rogers, a person's environment and themselves are inseparably linked. She held the view that a person's environment and themselves constitute a unified entity that must be studied as a whole. She also believes that after change occurs, neither humans nor their environment can go back to their previous state because both continue to evolve, change, and advance together (Boulding, 1956)

Nursing described as a humanistic and humanitarian art and science in Roger's philosophy of human beings. The science of unitary humans has two dimensions: the science of nursing, which is the knowledge particular to nursing that derives from scientific study, and the art of nursing, which is applying the science of nursing in inventive ways to improve patient outcomes. She stated that while talking about health and treatment, the patient and his surroundings cannot be separated. According to Rogers, the purpose of nursing is to direct and refocus patterns of interaction between energy fields in order to realize each person's full potential in terms of health. This strengthens the coherence and integrity of human beings.

By evaluating this unitary being, nurses can apply their knowledge, attitude, and practice from the science of nursing to change patient outcomes in the prevention and treatment of PU in the hospital. The link between the patient and

environment will facilitate the patient result of PU prevention and treatment. A patient's mobility, health, nutritional status, age, and tissue perfusion, as well as environmental factors like moisture, inadequate bedding, pressure, shear, and/or skin friction, as well as the use of a wheelchair or lower-limb prosthesis, can all be assessed by nurses to help prevent and treat PU. These two aspects of the human being and environment must be evaluated in order to provide patients with a holistic nursing care for the purposes of PU prevention and treatment. There is quality assurance guaranteeing the patient's outcome once the nurses' KAP assessment improves the patient's wellness and their environment.

III. RESEARCH METHODS AND DESIGN

We conducted a descriptive cross-sectional design that explored nurses' knowledge, attitudes and practices towards prevention of pressure ulcers at KCMC hospital. The hospital is located in the Moshi Municipality of Kilimanjaro region, Northern Tanzania. It is one of the four zonal referral hospitals in Tanzania, and serves over 15 million people a year. It has 26 departments with 312 working nurses. 141 nurses were conveniently selected from different departments. The study consisted of nurses working at KCMC hospital in August 2020. The selection of nurses based on the fact that they play a great role in prevention of pressure ulcers among patients.

Data collection was conducted from July to August 2020 using an English self-administered questionnaire. The participants were informed about the study and asked to consent by signing a consent form. The response of the participants was filled in the questionnaire for approximately 30 minutes for each participant.

Questions were used to assess practice on prevention of PU. Participants had to indicate whether yes or no for each item. Answers were coded either correct or wrong with reference to pre-established marking guide. Practice would be classified into high level of practice (for score of $\geq 80\%$), moderate level of practice (for score of 70%-79%) and low level of practice (for score $\leq 69\%$). Therefore, for each item, the score was either 0 or 1 to indicate incorrect or correct respectively.

The feedback was with high consistency even if some remarks did not lack. The literature review was generally reviewed on nurses' KAP for PU prevention and treatment. Data entered, cleaned and analyzed using statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 20. Data was cleaned using frequency analysis, any information that was missing or not clear was re-checked in the questionnaire. Descriptive analysis was done and categorical data was summarized. Means or median (measure of central tendency) and measure of dispersion were used to summarize continuous data while categorical data summarized by using percentages.

IV. RESULTS

➤ *Socio-Demographic Data for the Study Participants*

The findings unveiled that majority of participants (58.2%) were female. Their age ranged from 18 to 47 years. In addition, majority of the participants worked in inpatient surgery unit (36%) and marital status shows that (73.0%) was single, (24.8%) was married, (1.4%) separated and (0.7%) Widow/widower. In term of register were nurses (45.4%), while (28%) were in Enrolled nurse, Intern nurse were 16.3 and lastly were Volunteering nurse with (20.6%) The participants had degree were (16.3%) and majority (50.4%) of them had Diploma level, (33.3%) had Certificate level Table 1 shows that most participants had limited understanding about PU prevention and treatment, with the

exception of the question inquiring about the most vulnerable locations for developing PU.

However, regarding the evidence-based nursing interventions for PU prevention, participants, had scored percentage indicating a good knowledge. They were able to identify the correct evidence-based nursing intervention, such as level of Nurses' Knowledge towards prevention of pressure ulcers, the attitudes towards pressure ulcers prevention among nurses and the practice towards prevention of pressure ulcers among nurses as well as regular repositioning, mobilization, assess nutritional status, provide high protein nutritional supplements, involve the patient and family in care of PU and the patient's health status

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
18-27	97	68.8
28-37	15	10.6
38-47	6	4.2
47 and above	23	16.4
Gender		
Male	59	41.8
Female	82	58.2
Marital status		
Single	103	73.0
Married	35	24.8
Separated	2	1.4
Widow/widower	1	0.7
Education level attained		
Certificate	47	33.3
Diploma	71	50.4
Bachelor	23	16.3
Nursing title at KCMC hospital		
Registered nurse (RN)	64	45.4
Enrolled nurse (EN)	25	17.7
Intern nurse	23	16.3
Volunteering nurse	29	20.6

Table 1:- Social demographic characteristics of study participants (N=141)

➤ *The Level of Knowledge towards Pressure Ulcers Prevention among Nurses*

Majority of participating nurses had low level of knowledge (75.2%) towards prevention of pressure ulcers. More than one-third of nurses (71.6%) wrongly identified the correct time for hourly turning of pressure ulcer patients, similarly more than half of participants (56.7%) wrongly identified the instructed time for patients on wheel chair to

shift their weight. Also, 57.4% of nurses wrongly identified the use of hot water and soap may dry the skin and increase the risk of development of PU and the majority of nurses (84.4%) wrongly identified the use of ring cushions help prevent PU. Lastly, most of the nurses (95.7%) agreed that educational programs may reduce the incidence of PU (Table 2).

Statement	Frequency	Percentage
All hospitalized individuals at risk for pressure ulcers/bed sores should have a systematic skin inspection at least daily and those in long-term care at least once a week.		
Yes	117	83.0
No	24	17.0
All individuals should be assessed on admission to a hospital for risk of pressure ulcer development		
Yes	124	87.9
No	17	12.1
Persons confined to bed should be repositioned every 3 hours.		
Yes	101	71.6
No	40	28.4
Persons who can be taught should shift their weight every 30 minutes while sitting in a chair		
Yes	80	56.7
No	61	43.3
Hot water and soap may dry the skin and increase the risk for pressure ulcers/ bed sores		
Yes	60	42.6
No	81	57.4
Ring cushions helps to prevent bed sores/ pressure ulcers		
Yes	119	84.4
No	22	15.6
Immobility is a risk factor for pressure ulcer development?		
Yes	117	83.0
No	24	17.0
Incontinence is a risk factor for pressure ulcer development?		
Yes	36	25.5
No	105	74.5
Impaired nutrition is a risk factor for pressure ulcer development?		
Yes	45	31.9
No	96	68.1
Altered level of consciousness is a risk factor for pressure ulcer development?		
Yes	49	34.8
No	92	65.2

Table 2:- Level of Nurses' Knowledge towards prevention of pressure ulcers (N=141)

➤ *The attitudes towards pressure ulcers prevention among nurses*

Majority of nurses had positive attitude (61.7%) towards PU prevention. 92.9% of nurses argued that most PU can be avoided and 95% of nurses had quick response to assess and attend patients in regard to PU care and prevention.

40.9% of all nurses agreed to the fact that nurses are to be blamed for pressure ulcer development. Moreover, about a one quarter (36.9%) preferred their clinical judgment over any other pressure ulcer risk assessment tool available. Interestingly, 31.2% of all nurses prioritize treatment of pressure ulcer rather than prevention (Table 3).

Statement	Frequency	Percentage
Do you have a quick response/ need to assess and attend patients in regard to pressure ulcer care and prevention?		
Yes	134	95.0
No	7	5.0
Is it very difficult to prevent pressure ulcers from occurring?		
Yes	21	14.9
No	120	85.1
Are nurses to be blamed for pressure ulcer development?		
Yes	57	40.4
No	84	59.6
Pressure ulcer treatment is a greater priority than pressure ulcer prevention		
Yes	44	31.2
No	97	68.8
Most pressure ulcers can be avoided		
Yes	131	92.9
No	10	7.1
I am less interested in pressure ulcer prevention than other aspects of care		
Yes	36	25.5
No	105	74.5
My clinical judgment is better than any pressure ulcer risk assessment tool available to me		
Yes	52	36.9
No	89	63.1

Table 3:- The attitudes towards pressure ulcers prevention among nurses at KCMC

➤ *The Practice Towards Prevention of Pressure Ulcers among Nurses*

Table 4 indicate that most of the nurses (45.4%) had moderate level of practice towards prevention of pressure ulcers. Majority of nurses (89.4%) do provide health education patients regarding PU. 95.7% of all nurses, assist patients on improving Nutritional needs by advising on

supplements and Adequate fluid intake. Regarding assessment of the skin condition particularly on the prominent areas by checking intactness, color, sensation, temperature and moisture, majority of nurses (66.7%) took temperature in most consideration compared to other measures, of which it was regularly checked (Table 4).

Statement	Frequency	Percentage
Do you assess the skin conditions particularly on prominent areas by checking intactness		
Yes	73	51.8
No	68	48.2
Do you assess the skin conditions particularly on prominent areas by checking color		
Yes	86	61.0
No	55	39.0
Do you assess the skin conditions particularly on prominent areas by checking sensation		
Yes	47	33.3
No	94	66.7
Do you assess the skin conditions particularly on prominent areas by checking temperature		
Yes	44	31.2
No	97	68.8

Do you assess the skin conditions particularly on prominent areas by checking moisture		
Yes	75	53.2
No	66	46.8
I help patients manage fecal incontinence by; Toileting plan and soiling checks		
Yes	128	90.8
No	13	9.2
I assist patients on improving Nutritional needs by advising on; Supplements (protein, Vitamin A and for malnourished patients) and Adequate fluid intake.		
Yes	135	95.7
No	6	4.3
Do you provide patients and care givers with health education on pressure ulcer preventive measures before discharge		
Yes	126	89.4
No	15	10.6
I assist patients with feeding		
Yes	141	100
No	0	0

Table 4:- Nurses' practice towards prevention of pressure ulcers (N=141)

V. DISCUSSION

The primary factors that have been identified as contributing to PU prevention and treatment among patients with restricted mobility are nurses' knowledge, attitudes, and practices. The study's findings showed that 58.2 % of the participants were female, and for marital status 73.0 % of study participants were single, 17.7 % of them were enrolled nurse, 16.3% were intern nurse and lastly 20.6% were volunteering nurse. Nursing care has an impact on pressure ulcer development and prevention. Study findings show that nurses had low level of knowledge, positive attitude and moderate level of practice towards PU prevention among nurses. Failure to identify correctly risk factors of PU, repositioning of the bed ridden patients, ring cushions use and wheel chair weight shift all pointed to the low level of knowledge. Our findings are somehow inconsistent to the most of the hospital-based studies.

A study done by Clarke, (2005) in Canada across the continuum of care (primary, secondary and tertiary) in a Canadian urban Health Region showed 61.2% of nurses had adequate knowledge regarding PU prevention also study done by Laukkanen, (2016) in Finland showed 54.4% had good knowledge and this can be because most of the nurses attended different seminars and training concerning pressure ulcers contrary to our setting. On the other hand, most of the study participants were aware of the occurrence of the pressure ulcers around the bony prominences.

The level of Nurses' attitude towards prevention of pressure ulcers on prevention and treatment was found to be enough satisfied where by majority of nurses had positive attitude (61.7%) towards PU prevention and 92.9% of nurses argued that most PU can be avoided and 95% of nurses had

quick response to assess and attend patients in regard to PU care and prevention. 40.9% of all nurses agreed to the fact that nurses are to be blamed for pressure ulcer development. Their observation of the patient's PU during daily activities may have contributed to their high percentage whereas their low score percentage would have been explained by their lack of experience or get any PU-related in-service training.

Study by Demarré, (2014) shows that in-service training to help with PU prevention in Wollega zones after their study findings revealed that nurses' knowledge of PU prevention was insufficient (91.5%) among participants due to a lack of in-service training and self-documentation by reading published materials. These nurses had poor knowledge on several items as they responded that all patients are at high risk for developing PU (96%), treatment of PU is a higher priority than prevention, there is no assessment tool of predicting PU in their service and no continuous assessment of at-risk patients could give an accurate patients' outcomes and PU prevention is a higher priority than treatment. This may also be explained by the aforementioned rationale for the absence of clinical practice guidelines and in-service training or workshops.

With a non-negligible proportion of participants who had a negative attitude (more than 50%), the nursing staff had a good attitude toward PU prevention. The negative attitude for others study was observed among nurses who believe that preventing PU takes a lot of work and that patients don't seem to have as many PU anymore. These unfavorable attitudes may contribute to an increase in the incidence of PU among newly admitted patients, particularly for those who have risk factors. In order to improve their knowledge and, by extension, their attitude, in-service training should be implemented. In order to improve their knowledge and, by

extension, their attitude, in-service training should be implemented. In order to decrease the frequency of pressure ulcers by altering behavior patterns and thereby raise the degree of health professionals' knowledge regarding the prevention of pressure ulcers, training of health care workers is regarded as a crucial component of the prevention of PU.

Findings generally showed that nurses' practices were above the average and on all practical questions, participants' scores were above the average and could be attributed to the study's findings that no clinical practice guidelines existed for PU prevention and treatment among the nurses and that none of the participants had yet attended a workshop on the subject. Poor practice among nurses may be caused by the lack of in-service training and awareness sessions in some professional practice. Because nurses are primarily responsible for determining patient PU risk and managing skin integrity, the frequency of PU in healthcare settings is regarded as a sign of the quality of nursing care provided.

VI. RECOMMENDATIONS

As a non-negligible number of nurses participating nurses had low level of knowledge towards prevention of pressure ulcers and practice, the researchers believe that additional interventional studies are required to improve nurses' knowledge and practice in general with regard to PU prevention and treatment. Additionally, a study on the application of Evidence-based nursing practices (EBNP) for PU prevention and treatment might be carried out to enable nurses in hospital settings to apply it. In order to simplify this implementation, a clinical practice guideline for PU prevention and treatment might be created.

In order to improve students' nursing knowledge before they enter the clinical setting, it is highly advised that universities, and more specifically the nursing program, revise and update the curriculum in regards to PU prevention and treatment. It is also highly recommended that nurses engage in continuous professional development (CPD), and that its efficacy be regularly assessed. In order for nurses to provide the greatest nursing care in regards to PU prevention and treatment, which may result in the best patient outcome, protocols, guidelines, and assessment tools are also required and should be made available in services.

Lastly, the researcher also suggested that in order for policymakers to be able to take appropriate action, the incidence and prevalence of PU cases should be easily known at the central level and reported to the Ministry of Health, just like it is done for communicable and non-communicable diseases. Another idea to address these issues is to have healthcare professionals participate in seminars and workshops together so they may exchange knowledge and expertise and lessen the stigma associated with asking someone in another field for assistance.

The researcher Bauer, (K,2021) recommend nurses to partake in continuing professional development opportunities that could enhance patient care and mention how continuing education in nursing will help to become a better nurse. This

will also improve your professional service, promote collegial learning and interaction, give personal rewards, job security, and a commitment to your profession. The primary drivers for nurses to participate in continuing education have been determined to be personal advantages, professional progress and development, and job stability.

VII. CONCLUSION

This study showed that the nurse's low level of knowledge towards prevention of pressure ulcers. Even though their attitude did not show sound judgment, which could be the result of inadequate knowledge, their attitude was still positive. Continuous professional development (CPD) was advised as a solution to get around this obstacle. The greatest socio-demographic component that was connected to nurses' knowledge and attitude for PU prevention as well as treatment level of education. This study found a significant inverse relationship between nurses' practice and education levels as well as between their attitudes and knowledge. Understaffed wards have a lower chance of discovering pressure ulcers, and the nurses frequently feel unable to give the patients the attention they need. Another risk factor is a patient's ability to pay for healthcare, which makes it more likely that pressure ulcers may go untreated. The study's objective was to highlight the difficulties nurses in Tanzania face in identifying and treating pressure ulcers. Its conclusion is that education of healthcare professionals and patients is the key element that might make pressure ulcer diagnosis and prevention easier.

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